

**DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSPORT AND MACHINERY INDUSTRY
IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. After the independence of our country, today's demand is the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process in order to radically improve the service of transport to the economy and the population and to improve the transport management system. Therefore, the development of the transport and engineering sector, which is one of the leading sectors in the country in terms of economic growth, is one of the key areas.

Аннотация. После обретения нашей страной независимости сегодняшней потребностью является внедрение современных педагогических технологий в образовательный процесс с целью коренного улучшения транспортного обслуживания экономики и населения и

совершенствования системы управления транспортом. Поэтому развитие транспортно-машиностроительной отрасли, которая является одной из ведущих отраслей в стране по темпам экономического роста, является одним из ключевых направлений.

Keywords. Transport, machine building, Tashkent, Fergana economic region, automotive industry.

Ключевые слова. Транспорт, машиностроение, Ташкент, Ферганский экономический район, автомобилестроение.

Entrance. In the conditions of Uzbekistan's independence, as well as in the period of transition to a market economy, there are also certain opportunities in the field of machine-building industry, as well as a number of problems. During the time of the former Union, a number of machine-building factories established in our republic were closely connected with factories and enterprises of the former "sister" republics. The raw material resources needed for our factories were mainly brought from factories or raw material bases in those republics.

Main Part. We will divide the economic regions of our republic into 3 groups according to the availability of machine-building industry enterprises, the level of development, and location characteristics.

The first group includes the Tashkent economic district. This economic region is characterized by a highly developed and diversified machinery industry.

More than 20 branches of the machine-building industry are gathered here,

and 82% of the machine-building products produced in the whole republic are produced in them. 68% of the products produced in Kolaversa machinery industry are contributed by specialized machinery industries. In addition to the scientific-research and scientific-technical base for the development of the machine-building industry, this economic region also has highly qualified personnel. The main machine-building enterprises are characterized by labor-intensiveness and sufficiently high cultural productivity. The main factor limiting the economic region of Tashkent is the factor of environmental protection and rational use of nature. In particular, this can be explained by the consistent regulation of the construction of industrial enterprises in Tashkent.

From this point of view, the expansion of the production capacity of existing enterprises in the city and the increase of production due to extensive factors are limited. Therefore, one of the main tasks for large enterprises located in the Tashkent economic region is to place their shops and branches in some regions and small towns.

Currently, the production of mechanical engineering is highly concentrated in Tashkent, which accounts for more than 70% of the production of mechanical engineering.

This, in turn, deepens the inequality in the territory of the republic, and at the same time causes a number of problems related to the speed and scale of development of machine-building industries in this region.

The second group includes Fergana, Samarkand, Kashkadarya economic regions. They account for 5% to 12% of the republic's machine-building production. In this group, the most developed machine-building industries are production of machines for the automotive industry, electrotechnical industry, light and food industry.

The contribution of these industries is 20% of the product production of the whole republic. But all the specialized industries in these regions make up only 1% of the production of machine-building products of the whole republic.

When we evaluate the characteristics of the development of the machine-building industry in the economic regions belonging to this group, we see important differences between them. If in the future for the Fergana economic region, the main way is to intensify production and deepen specialization in the existing machine-building enterprises, then for the economic regions of Samarkand and Kashkadarya, the formation and organization of new machine-building industries is appropriate. In particular, in Kashkadarya, the electrical engineering industry is extremely weakly developed at the moment. In the Samarkand region, specialized machine-building industries are automotive transport and tool-making, machine tool-making, road-building machine-building, and electrical engineering are almost underdeveloped.

The most important decisive factor for the location of machine-building enterprises here is the availability of labor resources and population density. Placement and development of labor-intensive machine-building industries in these regions is not only of economic, but also of great social importance.

The third group includes Bukhara-Navoi, Lower Amudarya and Surkhandarya economic regions. Their characteristic feature is that the machine-building industries are extremely weakly developed in them, the republic produces 0.1-0.5% of the production volume of machine-building products.

Here we can distinguish industries such as chemical and petrochemical engineering, machine tool engineering, tractor engineering, and agricultural engineering.

This group of economic regions can rapidly develop machine-building industries at the expense of existing medium-sized and small cities and reserves of labor resources.

Until now, the development of the agricultural industrial complex in our republic has had a direct impact on the development of machine-building industries and the formation of its industries, and this situation will remain valid in the future.

In 1975-1999, there were certain changes in the formation and development of the territorial location of machine-building industries in Uzbekistan, which can be attributed to the formation of machine-building industries in regions where there were no machine-building enterprises before. In particular, in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in Kashkadarya, Navoi, Surkhandarya, and Khorezm regions, a number of machine-building industries were established. If in 1975 there were no machine-building industries in these regions, then in 1999 it will be 0.05%, 0.5%, 0.2% and 0.1%, respectively.

Regional engineering industry in Uzbekistan change in structure

1- table

Regions	1 975	1 990	2 000	2 015
Qoraqalpog'iston	-	0,	0,	0,
Andijon	6,	05	06	04
Buxoro	4	5,	5,	6,
Jizzax	0,	8	7	5
Kashqadaryo	4	0,	0,	0,
Navoiy	-	3	3	35
<i>Namangan</i>	-	0,	0,	0,
	-	1	1	17
Samarkand	1,	0,	0,	0,
Surxondaryo	6	05	07	1
Toshkent	5,	0,	0,	0,

Sirdaryo	4	2	2	23
Fargona	-	2,	2,	2,
Xorazm	1	1	2	0
Toshkent city	0	5,	5,	6,
	0,	7	6	0
	5	0,	0,	0,
	3,	1	08	1
	6	1	1	1
	-	0,1	0,1	0
	7	0,	0,	0,
	2,1	2	18	2
		3,	3,	3,
		7	6	1
		0,	0,	0,
		2	23	3
		7	7	7
		1,4	1,6	0,9
All together	1	1	1	1
	00	00	00	00

Territorial organization of the machine-building industry and increasing its efficiency is one of the most important ways to satisfy the national economy's demand for the products of this sector. In this regard, one of the most important tasks for the machine-building industry at present is the formation and improvement of new machine-building industries in Samarkand, Kashkadarya, Bukhara-Navoi, Kuyi Amudarya, Surkhandarya economic regions, as well as the production of machine-building products for animal husbandry, winemaking, horticulture, and vegetable growing. Implementation of these works would solve the problems of rational use of labor resources and formation of qualified labor resources from the local population in the listed economic regions.

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